

Countering Adversarial Attacks on Autonomous Vehicles Using Denoising Techniques: A Review

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ABSTRACT The evolution of automotive technology will eventually permit the automated driving system on the vehicle to handle all circumstances. Human occupants will be just passengers. This poses security issues that need to be addressed. This paper has two aims. The first one investigates strategies for robustifying scene analysis of adversarial road scenes. A taxonomy of the defense mechanisms for countering adversarial perturbations is initially presented, classifying those mechanisms in three major categories: those that modify the data, those that propose adding extra models, and those that focus on modifying the models deployed for scene analysis. Motivated by the limited number of surveys in the first category, we further analyze the approaches that utilize input transformation operations as countermeasures, further classifying them in supervised and unsupervised methods and highlighting both their strengths and weaknesses. The second aim of this paper is to publish CarlaScenes dataset produced using the CARLA simulator. An extensive evaluation study, on CarlaScenes, is performed testing the supervised deep learning approaches that have been either proposed for image restoration or adversarial noise removal. The study presents insights on the robustness of the aforementioned approaches in mitigating adversarial attacks in scene analysis operations.

INDEX TERMS Countering adversarial images, robust road scene analysis, deep learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE CONTINUOUSLY growing domain of Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) has gained interest in both academia and industry. AVs are considered as an integral component of connected intelligent transportation systems, improving the performance of transportation systems, providing safer transportation, efficient management of fuel consumption and upgrading the whole traveling experience.

One of the most essential operations executed at the AVs to enable the aforementioned benefits is the perception and understanding of dynamic and complex environments from multi-modal sensor data. The critical nature of the perception ability [1] in safety functions for autonomous

driving is self-evident: a deviation of, for example, 30 cm in the estimated lateral position of the autonomous vehicle can make all the difference between a “correct” and an “incorrect” (and, potentially, life-threatening) maneuver. One of the major challenges to be addressed is the highly dynamic behavior of road users (e.g., pedestrians, cyclists, cars), who can change their motion style in an instance, or start/stop moving abruptly. Consequently, prediction horizons for active perception systems are typically short; even so, small performance improvements can produce tangible benefits. For example, accident analyses [2] show that being able to initiate emergency braking 0.16 s earlier, at a time to a collision of 0.66 s, reduces the chance of incurring injury requiring a hospital stay from 50% to 35%, given an initial vehicle speed of 50 km/h.

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A well-known driving force towards addressing challenges related to fast and effective scene understanding solutions, is the advancement of machine learning (ML) methods, particularly deep learning (DL). The impressive ability of ML/DL to leverage increasingly accessible large volumes of data, generated by various multi-modal sensors (e.g., cameras, LiDAR, mechanical control units, etc.), along with the advancement in other concomitant technologies (such as wireless communications [3]), is expected to enable autonomous and self-organizing connected vehicles in the future. Especially in future vehicular networks that will enable ubiquitous Internet access on vehicles, ML will have a predominant role in the perception system of autonomous and semi-autonomous connected vehicles.

While ML/DL techniques come with big expectations, there are formidable challenges in dealing with carefully crafted adversarial perturbations [4]. In addition to the image-aware adversarial perturbations [4], Moosav-Dezfooli *et al.* [5] introduced ‘universal perturbations’ fooling a classifier for every image. Recently different physical world attacks (e.g., attacks on traffic signs [6], [7]) have been successfully performed on the vision system of autonomous vehicles with Deng *et al.* [8] analyzing five adversarial attacks on three different models used in the AV domain.

That has raised many privacy and security concerns [9], [10] about the usage of such methods particularly for security-critical applications, especially in AVs, which are equipped with many sensors. These share critical sensory information with onboard devices through CAN bus and with other nearby vehicles as well. Thus, cybersecurity rises out as a necessity to protect such systems and the information contained inside. Applied to the vehicles of today and the near future, cybersecurity needs to take on an even more important role: to protect systems and components that govern safety from harmful cyberattacks, unauthorized access, damage, or anything else that might interfere with safety functions.

The impact of cyber-attacks on an industry, such as the Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) could be tremendous [11]. Taking into consideration the current architectures in the automotive industry, an external attacker can potentially gain access to every aspect of the vehicle, including the most sensitive ones. They can steal personal information and manipulate sensors data. Even worse, they can threaten drivers’ physical safety with the potential to hijack the whole system. Not only does this kind of attack risk the lives of drivers and pedestrians, but it raises great consequences for the reputation of the industry. Thus, there is an increasing interest in both academia and industry to proactively address modern vehicle cybersecurity challenges applying advanced Artificial Intelligence (AI) and ML techniques, and also to continuously seek methods to mitigate associated safety risks. For instance, Kyrkou *et al.* [12] highlighted the role of AI and ML techniques in modern autonomous vehicle cybersecurity challenges and how they can mitigate associated safety risks.

Adversarial training (AT) [13] has been widely adopted to safeguard deep neural networks from external attackers. AT targets modifying the model’s parameters by minimizing empirical risk for a given data distribution together with the various perturbed images. The aforementioned strategy results in several challenges, including i) task dependency affecting training overhead, ii) computational overhead that restricts its utilization to high-dimensional and large datasets, iii) accuracy drop [14] and iv) label leakage, allowing models to over-fit on perturbations, thus affecting model generalization to unseen adversaries. Alternatively to AT, input processing methods provide also promising results in mitigating adversarial noise. They are scalable and more effective to large datasets and can work across different tasks (e.g., object detection and/or segmentation). Though, it should be mentioned that there are cases, where input transformations maximize attack strength, instead of minimizing it [15].

In this paper, we aim to present a high-level overview of both supervised and unsupervised methods that can be used as a defense mechanism for adversarial attacks. These mechanisms are considered as a denoising block that will precede the execution of the ML/DL model, while adversaries are considered as noise that corrupts the original image. If we apply a transformation to the original images before feeding them to the perception model of the autonomous vehicle, the effect of the adversarial example would be significantly eliminated, as it will become also evident in the following studies. Moreover, a dataset dedicated to automotive scenarios is released in which the ability of defense methods in mitigating attacks from adversaries is tested. The following are the major contributions of this study:

- We thoroughly investigate how adversarial manipulations affect scene analysis operations that are executed in AVs.
- We provide a taxonomy of the defense mechanisms that utilize input transformation operations as countermeasures considering both supervised and unsupervised approaches.
- We present an extensive study, where we evaluate the ability of various SoA methods that have been either proposed for image restoration or for adversarial noise removal in mitigating adversarial examples in scene analysis operations.
- A large dataset is generated using the CARLA autonomous driving simulator and can be effectively deployed for studying the robustness of defense approaches on adversarial images used for scene analysis tasks in autonomous driving tasks.
- Finally, we highlight various open research problems.

II. AVS: HISTORY AND CHALLENGES

Undoubtedly the field of autonomous vehicles (AVs) is continuously evolving and poses plenty of new challenges. When referring to an intelligent transportation system (ITS), AVs can not be excluded from the equation. It is of crucial importance to make decisions with high certainty and quite

FIGURE 1. A typical AV system composed of three functional layers sensing, perception, and planning layer combined with an overview of attacks on each submodule.

FIGURE 2. A graphical representation of levels of driving automation.

agile using critical information (e.g., traffic and road conditions) gathered from sensors (e.g., Cameras, Lidar, Radar, IMU/GPS) or exchanged through communication channels. The amount and complexity of data that need to be processed make ML/DL methods a necessity in the decision-making process. As the automation level increases more and more decisions are being made by the control unit.

The level of automation of a vehicle has a graduation from no automation at all, to full automation. Following [16] five categories are being distinguished and are graphically represented in Figure 2 with a distinction based on who monitors the system.

As the automation level increases, the processing layers that comprise the system of an AV become fully automated increasing the access points that malicious users can exploit to disrupt the normal behavior of the car. A high-level representation of the layer encompassing an AV alongside the possible entry points of an attacker is shown in Figure 1. The AV system is represented by three functional layers sensing, perception, and decision layer. The sensing layer includes different sensors to collect surrounding information around an AV. The perception layer extracts information from the scene, e.g., scene segmentation, objects, flow, obstacles. The

decision layer is responsible for path planning, vehicle control, etc. Every layer is susceptible to different kinds of attacks. An attack could be performed directly on the sensing layer by sending signals of the same frequency sensors to operate (e.g., jamming [17], spoofing attacks [18]) or by intervening in the communications channel (e.g., eavesdropping [19], sybil attacks [19]) [20] of AVs. ML/DL model used for perception could also be affected and as presented in [4], can be easily fooled by adversaries. Following the pattern of [21] the ways of attack could be divided into four generic categories:

A. ATTACKS ON VEHICULAR ADHOC NETWORK (VANET)

For the communication to be established on connected vehicles, networks known as vehicular ad-hoc networks (VANETs) are used [22]. When a vehicle or an infrastructure is connected to the VANET the communication among them is allowed, which gives various capabilities. Information about traffic, road condition, vehicle or pedestrian position could help to avoid accidents or traffic jams. Although the networks could also be the access point for an external attacker. The security on internal networks could be compromised in multiple ways, i.e., passcode and key attacks. For instance, eavesdropping [19] on a wireless connection could give the attacker access to private data (e.g., location). In the same length sybil attack is the situation where a malicious vehicle transmits the various messages with multiple fake or stolen source identities to other nodes. Overall wireless communications established through WiFi, Bluetooth and GSM protocols are not completely secure [23] and hold important information which can be utilized by intruders.

B. ATTACKS ON SENSORS EXPLOITING THEIR VULNERABILITIES

External users aiming to manipulate the sensors of the vehicle employ the same physical channels as the sensor they target. These sensors are normally trusted by users as being the lower layers of a control system. However, falsified measurements could lead to unexpected results for the whole

FIGURE 3. Autonomous vehicle's major sensor types, their range, and position (figure adopted from [25]).

system. Saturating/Jamming the lidar [18], blinding the camera [18], spoofing the signal of GPS [18] or the lidar [17] are some of the attacks that can have a significant effect on the vehicle's behavior. For instance, Vitale *et al.* [24] focus on the H2020-CAMEL project, which addresses the cybersecurity gaps introduced by the new technological domains. More specifically, in [24], the potential threats and vulnerabilities on the vehicle's sensors, i.e., the GPS receiver, have been presented. In sensor attacks, it is assumed that the attacker is outside the vehicle and targets sensor data acquisition. Figure 3 indicates the major sensor types, range, and position of an AV.

C. EXPLOITING HARDWARE TO ATTACK

If the attacker, i.e., repair mechanic, gains access to the hardware of the autonomous vehicle he could directly exploit the sensor data, cause damage to the communication modules or even inject virus or malware into the framework of the vehicle. For instance, he could update the firmware of the Engine Control Unit (ECU), by reflashing it with custom libraries and provoking malicious functionalities and actions.

D. ADVERSARIAL ATTACKS ON AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES

As deep neural networks are being used more extensively, more research should be conducted in this field to create secure and stable applications. Adversaries can alter original inputs with perturbations, which may be imperceptible to the human eye, but can force a trained model to produce incorrect outputs. Szegedy *et al.* [4] first discovered that state-of-art deep neural networks are vulnerable to adversarial perturbations. It seems that adversaries take huge advantage of the non-linearity of DNNs combined with the insufficient regularization techniques used in the majority of learning problems. Studies on attacks from adversaries have developed attacks for image classification models [13], used

for multiple vision tasks such as object detection [26], [27], object tracking [28], and semantic segmentation [27]. A comprehensive study toward adversarial robustness was that of Arnab *et al.* [29]. They evaluated the robustness of popular DCNN models used for segmentation tasks against adversarial manipulations and concluded that the accuracy of the models seriously decreased after the original image has been perturbed. Adversaries have also been discovered to be mistaken by DCNNs for traffic legitimate traffic signs [6], [30]. The aforementioned methods were producing attacks that target to fool the camera sensor. Processing raw 3D point clouds, coming from LiDAR sensor, with DCNNs are also venerable to adversaries as denoted by [31]. The study of [31] is evaluated with a single digital model while in [32] a differential renderer used to simulate the reconstructed laser beams projecting onto object surfaces to evaluate the adversarial attacks.

Overall, there exist two types of adversarial attacks: evasion and poisoning attacks. In evasion attacks, the attacker tampers test data to have them misclassified. As a result, the evasion attack on the machine learning model is performed during inference. The idea is to design input data with specific properties, which seem imperceptible to the human eye but can manipulate the target model's behavior and provide wrong decisions. On the other hand, poisoning attacks consist of tampering training samples to purposely compromise the perception layer to cause a denial of service. There are multiple ways to manipulate the target model using a poisoning attack, such as logic corruption, data manipulation, data injection, or transfer learning. Poisoning attack during transfer learning is more applicable to AVs since a DNN trained for image classification could be further trained to recognize traffic signs. For instance, GU *et al.* [33] investigated backdooring attacks on DNNs and proposed that more research should be conducted in this specific field. They have mentioned that an attacker may have the opportunity

FIGURE 4. The impact of adversarial attacks in an application related to AVs, such as segmentation of the scene. The images were generated using the simulator of CARLA [39].

to provide the driver with a backdoored street sign detector that has high accuracy for classifying traffic signs in normal conditions but classifies stop signs with a particular sticker on them as speed limit signs. They proved that backdoors in pre-trained networks can survive transfer learning, such that the final model also misbehaves when it sees backdoored images.

As regards the perception layer, an extensive evaluation has been conducted in the experimental section to investigate the effect of adversarial attacks on the task of semantic segmentation. Finally, the decision layer is not included in the scope of this paper, but in Fig. 1 some of the applications that could be tampered with adversarial or other attacks have been illustrated, such as path planning or ego-motion estimation.

III. ADVERSARIAL ATTACKS FOR AVS

As DL algorithms have been exploited more and more by the automotive industry, the security and robustification of these algorithms should be our main concern. Adversaries can easily tamper data coming from multiple sensors of an AV, which may be imperceptible by humans, but can manipulate the vehicle's behavior. An example is illustrated in Figure 4, in which a part of the vehicle has been disappeared from the camera sensor.

An extensive review of the representative adversarial examples and defense mechanisms that existed in the literature has been conducted [8], [34], [35], [36], [37], [38]. More specifically Chakraborty *et al.* [34] and Akhtar and Mian [35] presented the majority of manipulations from adversaries and state of art response mechanisms. One step further Liu *et al.* [36] presented in a data-driven manner the security threats and defenses from adversarial attacks making a distinction between the training phase and the inferring phase. Ren *et al.* [38] gave more emphasis on the theoretical foundations of techniques, and recent applications of manipulations from adversaries. Several defense mechanisms aiming to alleviate the adversarial perturbations are provided as well. Deng *et al.* [8] presented an in-depth overview of the various challenges associated with adversarial threats focusing exclusively on autonomous driving models. Finally, Qayyum *et al.* [37] focus on adversarial

threats on connected and autonomous driving models. ML pipeline of CAVs is also presented which indicates various potential security issues correlated with the adoption of ML methods.

Overall despite the comprehensive analysis of the vulnerabilities posed by adversaries that have been conducted there is a limited amount of surveys tackling the issues of these attacks on AVs. Taking that into consideration and the fact that there is a huge variety of denoising methods in the literature that have been proposed for classic image restoration problems, we propose to apply these methods for adversarial noise removal. Thus, we further present the approaches that utilize input transformation operations as countermeasures, by exploring a variety of networks trained on either adversarial or other types of noise.

A. ADVERSARIAL THREAT MODEL

To increase the success rate of the attack, the adversary tries to identify the vulnerabilities of the AV system. Figure 1 demonstrates an overview of the possible entry points of the attacks on the system of the autonomous vehicle. One of them could be by attacking the data that will be collected from different sensors (Cameras, Lidar, Radar, IMU/GPS) of an autonomous vehicle. This could be achieved by adding a sticker to a vehicle, traffic sign, or even a trash bin [4], [6], [30]. Szegedy *et al.* [4] studied the properties of neural networks and managed to cause the network to misclassify an image by applying a certain hardly perceptible perturbation. One step further Shen *et al.* [40] proposed unrestricted adversarial examples using conditional generative adversarial networks for semantic segmentation models. They validated their approaches on the datasets of Cityscapes [41] and ADE20K [42] and increased the success rate of attack by up to 41.0% compared with the SoA methods. 3D printed adversarial objects could also affect the lidar efficiency [31], [32], [43]. Liu *et al.* [43] investigated the adversarial attacks on 3D classifiers. They concluded that 3D point cloud classifiers, such as PointNet [44] or PointNet++ [45] are weak to adversaries leading to a high attack success rate. Another possible target could also be the algorithms utilized for the processing of the data (e.g., repair mechanic installing hacking device [46]). To analyze all possible scenarios, we can divide the threat models into two categories. The first one refers to the knowledge that the adversary has, while the other to the method for generating an adversarial example.

1) ADVERSARY'S KNOWLEDGE

As regards the first category, the threat model can be subdivided into black-box, grey-box and white-box.

1) Black-box model: the structure of the targeted architecture and its parameters are unknown to the adversary. However, input data could be sent to the network in order to analyze the targeted structure and identify potential vulnerabilities. Hence, acting as an oracle the external attacker can observe the model outputs to receive some substantial properties and compromise the targeted model.

2) Grey-box model: the attacker has additional information about the structure of the targeted network. There is no information about the specific weights or parameters of the network, but the whole architecture of the model is known. As a result, a grey-box adversary provides a bigger attack success rate compared to a black-box adversary.

3) White-box model: the adversary has total knowledge of the targeted network. In this case, both the parameters and the structure of the model are known. Also, the intruder has knowledge about the training phase and everything related to training data, hyper-parameters, activation functions, etc. Therefore, taking into consideration all of the above information, the adversary can easily detect potential vulnerabilities of the targeted model and generate strong attacks fooling easily the model.

2) METHODS FOR GENERATING ADVERSARIAL EXAMPLES

Definitions and Nomenclature: This paragraph will clarify the basic definitions and notations for the reader to understand the following equations of an adversarial example. The adversarial input of a model (\mathbf{M}) which from now on will be symbolized with x^* is equal to $x + \Delta_x$, where x is the original input to the model and Δ_x is the applied perturbation; ϵ is the maximum magnitude of the perturbation and consequently, we can write $\|\Delta_x\|_\infty < \epsilon$. For machine learning tasks that have targets, y is the targets associated with x . Moreover $J(x, y)$ denotes the loss function used to train the learning model and $J(x^*, y)$ represents the cross-entropy loss of a target classifier. In most cases the L_p norm of the adversarial noise is required to be less than an allowed value ϵ as $\|x^* - x\|_p \leq \epsilon$, where p could be 0, 1, 2, ∞ .

Taxonomy: There are several approaches [34], [47] aiming to generate strong manipulations from adversaries with a high error rate, so as to manipulate the vehicle's behavior. This paper will focus on adversarial attacks targeting the camera sensor. Methods for generating adversaries can be split into three categories, one-step gradient-based, iterative and optimization-based methods. Untargeted adversarial attacks will be explained firstly in the following paragraphs.

1) One-step Gradient-based approaches: This type of attack desires to find an adversarial example x^* by maximizing the loss function $J(x^*, y)$. Loss functions are used to determine the error between the output of \mathbf{M} and the given target value y . A representative approach is Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM) [13], [48] which generates adversarial examples based on the described approach, so as to meet the L_∞ norm bound $\|x^* - x\|_\infty \leq \epsilon$ as:

$$x^* = x + \epsilon \cdot \text{sign}(\Delta_x J(x, y)), \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta_x J(x, y)$ is the gradient of the relevant cost function. The Fast Gradient Method (FGM) is a generalization of FGSM to meet the L_2 norm bound $\|x^* - x\|_2 \leq \epsilon$ as:

$$x^* = x + \epsilon \cdot \frac{\Delta_x J(x, y)}{\|\Delta_x J(x, y)\|_2}. \quad (2)$$

FIGURE 5. From left to right: Input image and original segmentation output.

2) Iterative methods: These methods iteratively apply the fast gradient multiple times with a small step size α . The iterative version of FGSM (I-FGSM) or the Basic Iterative Method (BIM) [49], [50] use x for initialization in iteration $t = 0$:

$$x_0^* = x \quad (3)$$

and then a step similar to equation (1) from the FGSM is performed:

$$x_{t+1}^* = x_t^* + \alpha \cdot \text{sign}(\Delta_x J(x_t^*, y)). \quad (4)$$

To satisfy the L_∞ (or L_2) bound, we can clip x_t^* into the ϵ vicinity of x or simply set $\alpha = \epsilon/T$, with T declaring the amount of iterations. Hence, by clipping pixel values of intermediate results after each step, we make sure that the majority of them are in an ϵ -neighborhood of the original image. Variations of attacks falling into this category are Projected Gradient Descent [51], A-PGD [52] and Momentum Iterative Attack [47]. Also, multiple studies have shown that iterative approaches are more efficient in white box adversaries than the one-step methods.

3) Optimization-based methods: Optimizing the distance between the real and adversarial example is the goal of these methods in order to make the algorithm misclassify. One way to solve that problem is by using Box-constrained L-BFGS [53]. It can be expressed as:

$$\arg \min_{x^*} \lambda \cdot \|x^* - x\|_p - J(x^*, y). \quad (5)$$

Since the above equation directly optimizes the distance between an adversarial example and the corresponding real example, there is no guarantee that the L_∞ (L_2) distance is less than the required value. Also, these types of methods cannot provide a high error rate in black-box attacks, just like iterative methods. Finally, one attack which belongs to this category is Carlini and Wagner [53].

The previous methods can be applied for targeted attacks as well. The targeted FGSM attack, as a one-step gradient-based approach maximizes the probability of some specific target class, which is unlikely the true class for a given example. The adversarial example is crafted using the equation:

$$x^* = x - \epsilon \cdot \text{sign}(\Delta_x J(x, y)). \quad (6)$$

To visualize the impact of the adversarial attacks on the applications related to AVs, we trained the Deeplabv3 [54] segmentation network using the published dataset and tested it on attacked images. For illustration, in Figures 5 and 6 we can observe the output result of Deeplabv3, which takes

FIGURE 6. From left to right: Input image and original segmentation output.

TABLE 1. Adversarial attacks in Deeplabv3 [54] using multiple levels of perturbation and ϵ denotes the perturbation's amplitude.

TABLE 2. Adversarial attacks in Deeplabv3 [54] using multiple levels of perturbation and ϵ denotes the perturbation's amplitude.

as input benign images from our dataset. For illustration, in Figures 5 and 6 we can observe the segmentation output of Deeplabv3 [54] trained on the published dataset. In comparison Tables 1 and 2 take the clean Figures 5, 6 and perform different attacks with different levels of manipulation. The untargeted attacks of FGSM, BIM, and PGD were evaluated. At least visually, the accuracy of the segmentation model is affected more and more as the magnitude of the attack increases, especially in the BIM case, as is shown in the corresponding Tables 1, 2. A more extensive evaluation has been conducted and the previous deduction has been validated and presented in the experimental section.

IV. COUNTERMEASURES OF ADVERSARIAL ATTACKS

A variety of algorithms that function as defense mechanisms to adversaries have been proposed. Most of them are adaptive to specific types of adversarial attacks omitting,

though, all the others. Some of these defense mechanisms may also increase the complexity of the actual model, leading to performance overhead. However, these mechanisms manage to build robust algorithms aiming to mitigate adversarial effects on AVs, but further research efforts in this critical area should be provoked. Based on [37], the methods used to defend adversarial attacks can be split into three categories, modifying data, adding extra models and modifying models. A graphical taxonomy of them is illustrated in Figure 7.

A. MODIFY DATA

This category consists of techniques that modify either the training data or its features. The most representative methods are described below.

- 1) *Feature Denoising*: It refers to methods aiming to suppress much of the adversarial noise in the feature maps of the target network and focus only on the essential part of the input data. Many convolutional architectures have been already published aiming to solve the aforementioned problem. For instance, Xie *et al.* [55] proposed a solution that combines denoising filters with adversarial training leading to the improvement of the SoA in adversarial robustness in both white-box and black-box attacks. Another work-related to feature denoising was proposed by Liao *et al.* [56]. He introduced a high-level representation guided denoiser as a defense for image classification. Aiming to overcome the problem of the amplification effect of adversarial noise, Liao *et al.* trained a U-net [57] for denoising, replacing the pixel-level loss function with the reconstruction loss of the target model's outputs.
- 2) *Input Transformation*: Modifying data to remove any adversarial perturbation and then feeding them to the target model, is another defense mechanism. The non-differentiable and random nature of these techniques makes them one of the best defense algorithms that existed in the literature. Guo *et al.* [58] studied input transformations, such as bit-depth reduction, JPEG compression, total variance (TV) minimization, and image quilting showing great performance in multiple attacks. Also, Das *et al.* [59] investigated the effect of JPEG compression on adversaries proving that it could form a mitigation technique for attackers.
- 3) *Adversarial Training*: This method was first described by Goodfellow *et al.* [13]. The core idea is to inject adversarial inputs to the training set. Hence, augmenting these perturbed data, the target model improves not only its robustness to adversaries but also the generalization performance to benign inputs. Madry *et al.* [51] proved that adversarial training makes deep learning networks more resistant and reliable to adversaries. However, the results from the conducted experiments on the small MNIST dataset [60] could not reach the same level of performance in the dataset of CIFAR-10 [61]. Tramèr *et al.* [62] proved that adversarial training remains vulnerable to black-box attacks.

FIGURE 7. Taxonomy of defense mechanisms to adversarial attacks: i) add extra model, ii) modify model and iii) modify data.

B. ADD EXTRA MODEL

This category consists of methods aiming to exploit additional models to increase the resilience of the target model to adversarial attacks. Two approaches are described below, adversarial detection and ensemble algorithms.

- 1) *Adversarial Detection*: Adversarial detection is performed by using a binary classifier which is trained to know when input is legitimate or not [63], [64]. In [65] authors proposed to augment DNNs with a detector subnetwork. Their objective was the distinction between benign and contaminated with adversarial noise data. In the same direction, authors in [66] introduced an outlier class while training the DNN model. The model classifies the adversarial inputs as outliers. This approach has been widely used in the literature.
- 2) *Ensemble Algorithms*: The goal here is to combine different methods that could run in parallel aiming to defend against adversaries and provide improved situational awareness. Song *et al.* [67] implemented an algorithm based on this category. It was evaluated in the datasets of Fashion MNIST [60] and CIFAR-10 [68] and proved to be very effective in a wide variety of attacks.

C. MODIFY MODEL

This category consists of techniques that modify either the parameters or the features of each model. The most dominant approaches are described below:

- 1) *Gradient Hiding*: This method takes place when the defense mechanism hides valuable information about the gradient, making it difficult for any adversary to use it for the attack generation. However, methods falling into this category provide a false sense of security in defenses against adversaries [69].
- 2) *Defensive Distillation*: The idea of distillation was firstly introduced by Hinton *et al.* [70] as a mechanism aiming to transfer knowledge from a bigger model to a smaller one. That mechanism was adopted from Papernot *et al.* [71] to generate a defense algorithm against adversarial attacks. Defensive distillation was evaluated on multiple DNN architectures, showing that it manages to increase the robustification of DNN models to these attacks.

- 3) *Network Verification*: In general, each network consists of some specific properties and features. Hence, one way to detect an adversarial input could be to examine if it satisfies some specific properties. So, network verification aims to provide the previous feature to networks and constrain new unseen adversarial examples. For example, Katz *et al.* [72] proposed a technique for verifying properties of deep neural networks using Rectified Linear Unit activation function.

The rest of this paper will focus only on input transformation techniques. It is divided into two parts presented chronologically. The first one is referred to traditional low-level image processing techniques used to remove non-adversarial noise. While the second one describes input transformation defenses trained to remove adversarial noise specifically.

V. HOW TRADITIONAL LOW-LEVEL IMAGE PROCESSING CAN MITIGATE ADVERSARIAL NOISE?

There exists a vast amount of papers in the literature addressing the topic of the image restoration problem. However, most of the methods are not tested in adversarial noise. The predominant approaches for image restoration have been working mostly with Gaussian noise and similar random noise models to corrupt images. The approach in [73] is a first attempt to test a classic CNN-based restoration network on adversarial examples. The authors point out that misclassifications could be corrected by utilizing deep image restoration networks by learning to remove the adversarial perturbations from images and map the natural image manifold. It seems that these techniques achieve better results against several defenses [58], [74], [75], [76] implemented exclusively for adversarial noise. Adding to that [77] highlights the close connections between the adversarial robustness and corruption robustness research programs, and emphasizes the strong connection in the case of additive Gaussian noise. Both the adversarial and corruption robustness communities seem to have goals closely related. Several experiments have been conducted as presented in the last section that points out that the existing restoration networks could denoise adversarial attacked images quite well. When the denoising models have been trained to be effective on Gaussian noise with certain σ they can be effective on

FIGURE 8. Taxonomy of state-of-the-art unsupervised denoising domains.

adversarial attacks with the respective noise level. So they can be used as a model-agnostic defense mechanism against a wide range of recently proposed adversarial examples. In the next section, a review of the most dominant denoising approaches will be presented focusing mainly on the supervised denoising techniques.

A. UNSUPERVISED TRADITIONAL RESTORATION TECHNIQUES

This field has been particularly active in the first decade of this century, and most of the work in the second decade revolved around well-established methods, offering only small increments in the novelties, as we can see from recent reviews [78], [79]. An explanation for this observation is the big bang of Deep Learning in the second half of the last decade, which made many active researchers shift their focus to supervised techniques for denoising among other image processing tasks. Classic unsupervised denoising algorithms can be broadly divided into spatial and transform domain filtering. See Figure 8 for a graphical representation. Analyzing the aforementioned categories in depth is not in the scope of the paper so an overview will be presented that gathers several major works in the field of unsupervised denoising methods. Detailed survey papers can be found in [78], [79], [80], [81].

1) SPATIAL DOMAIN FILTERING

The main principle of the image denoising algorithm is that intensities of the true signal are correlated amongst pixels in contrast to noise intensities [82]. Spatial domain denoising exploits the correlation amongst the pixel candidates. The group of operations is employed directly on the image in comparison with the case of transform domain filtering where the corresponding transformations are first applied to the image and then thresholding is performed. Filters applied to the image can be classified as a local filter and a non-local filter. Local filters support denoising pixels within a spatial distance while non-local filters investigate the correlation amongst the pixels of the entire image.

2) TRANSFORM DOMAIN FILTERING

In this case, there is the observation that the characteristics of image information and noise are different in the transform domain. Methods falling into this category were initially inspired from the Fourier transform, but gradually other domain methods have emerged (e.g., cosine transform [83], wavelet domain methods [84], [85]), and block-matching and 3D filtering (BM3D) [86]). The given image was being transformed into another domain and then the denoising algorithm was being applied. According to the chosen basis transform functions, transform domain filtering methods can be divided into data-adaptive or non-data adaptive [87].

B. SUPERVISED TRADITIONAL RESTORATION TECHNIQUES

Unsupervised image restoration methods performed satisfying in image denoising problems. However, the aforementioned classical methods have two major drawbacks [88]. Firstly, these approaches are non-convex, so many of their parameters need to be defined manually. Secondly, classical methods form complex optimization problems and the computation cost that is required at the testing phase is relatively high compared with supervised techniques. This is the main reason why more emphasis is given to supervised image restoration methods both in the review and the experimental section. A review of the most dominant supervised approaches chronologically is presented in the sequel.

The great progress of deep neural networks (DNNs) has boosted the domain of computer vision tasks. One of the first attempts that tried to incorporate deep neural networks for image denoising is the one of Jain and Seung in [89]. Jain and Seung [89] trained a simple CNN with only four hidden layers and got better results compared to traditional methods, such as wavelet transform and Markov Random Fields(MRF). In 2012 Xie *et al.* [90] presented a training scheme that successfully adapts stacked sparse denoising auto-encoder originally designed for unsupervised feature learning, to the tasks of image denoising and blind inpainting which could achieve comparable performance with the K-singular value decomposition (K-SVD) algorithm [91]. Approaches towards the direction of neural networks were continued by [92]. They attempted to learn the mapping from a noisy image to a noise-free image by using a plain multi-layer perceptron (MLP) applied to image patches. It is a simple feed-forward neural network. The main contribution of this work was the proof that training on large image databases competed with the previous state-of-art learning free methods [86], [91], [93]. A pure learning approach was proposed without making assumptions about natural images as previous methods imposed.

In order to overcome the major drawbacks of the classic denoising technique's, i.e., BM3D [86], LSSC [94], WNNM [95], several discriminative learning methods have been developed to learn image prior models in the context of truncated inference procedure. Researchers in [96], [97] are able to get rid of the iterative optimization procedure

in the test phase and decrease the computational power that previous methods demanded. In [96], it was introduced a cascade of shrinkage fields (CSF) method that unifies the random field-based model and the unrolled halfquadratic optimization algorithm into a single learning framework. It outperforms the strongest competitor BM3D [86] with faster run-time. In [97] the framework TNRD, Trainable Nonlinear Reaction Diffusion, was proposed based on the concept of nonlinear reaction-diffusion models for various image restoration problems such as Gaussian image denoising, single image super-resolution and JPEG deblocking. TNRD [97] is a dynamic nonlinear reaction-diffusion model with time-dependent parameters. TNRD [97] leads to the best-reported performance by preserving the structural simplicity of diffusion models and taking only a small number of diffusion steps. It has comparable denoising results when compared with [86], [95], [96], although the method is generally faster with the same model capacity and it is applicable in high-resolution images due to its small memory requirements. Although CSF [96] and TNRD [97] have shown promising results toward bridging the gap between computational efficiency and denoising quality, their performance are inherently restricted to the specified forms of prior. To be specific, the priors adopted in these two methods are based on the analysis model, which is limited in capturing the full characteristics of image structures. Hence, many authors tried to model the problem as a plain discriminative learning problem, i.e., extracting the noise from a noisy image by using feed-forward convolutional neural networks (CNN).

The following success of CNNs started the area of deep learning with the popular networks AlexNet in ImageNet [98], GoogleNet [99], Highway network [100], ResNet [14] and several similar works revealing that the network depth is of crucial importance. Due to their plug-and-play network architectures, many researchers used them for image restoration tasks. Apart from their flexibility for exploiting image characteristics, CNNs can run with parallel computation on GPU, which decreases by far the run time performance, making it appropriate for using the denoising methods in the AVs domain. Moreover the improvement of the learning methods and regularization of CNNs, i.e., including Rectifier Linear Unit (ReLU) [98], batch normalization [101] and residual learning [14], have boosted the training process and improved the denoising performance.

Starting with Mao *et al.* [102] in 2016, skip connections between corresponding convolutional and deconvolutional layers were suggested to suppress the noise and retrieve the original images. The role of these connections is to back-propagate the gradients to bottom layers and let image characteristics be handled by top layers, allowing a more productive train of the end-to-end mapping. In 2017 researchers designed and trained a set of fast and effective CNN denoisers [103] for image denoising. In detail, by exploiting the variable splitting technique, they adopted the learned denoiser to a model-based optimization method of half

quadratic splitting to restore the quality of blurred and low-resolution images. In [88] it is pointed out that residual learning and batch normalization can benefit one another. Integrating them into the model can reduce its training time and boost accuracy. A pre-trained DnCNN under σ can not manipulate compression and interpolation errors of other noise variances. For the use cases that the noise level can not be estimated the denoising method should be adopted by a user-defined factor, to define the trade-off between quality protection and noise suppression.

The user-directed approach was introduced by [104]. FFDNet [104] uses as a controlling factor the noise level which makes it feasible to be adopted to various noises. Another major contribution of FFDNet is the reduction of the training and testing phase by working on down-sampled sub-images. Consequently, it expands the receptive field. In 2019, the Adaptive Feature Modification Layers (AdaFm) [105] was introduced in a step toward handling continual modulation of restoration levels. AdaFm facilitates consecutive modulation of the restoration strength without using much computational power. At first, a standard restoration CNN is trained for the start level, and then AdaFM layers are inserted to optimize it to the end level. After the training stage, CNN parameters are being fixed. The filters of AdaFM layers are adopted to the testing restoration level by interpolating their coefficients. By using a controlling parameter the CNN can progressively and interactively handle the restoration results/effects.

Another interesting approach [106] aiming to optimize the resource handling of the model was built by fully convolutional networks (FCN). In a denoising procedure where the input and output data usually are of the same dimensions, one ordinary strategy is to remove the pooling layers from the FCNs. However, the receptive field size is decreased for FCN without pooling. Having a larger receptive field means that restoration performance utilizes more spatial information. To enlarge the receptive field, in [106] a multi-level wavelet CNN (MWCNN) model was proposed by keeping a good trade-off between efficiency and performance. Moreover, [106] is a U-Net architecture consisting of a contracting subnetwork and an expanding subnetwork. They are using discrete wavelet transform (DWT) and inverse wavelet transform (IWT). DWT is used in the contracting subnetwork as a replacement for each pooling operation while in the expanding subnetwork IWT upsamples feature maps of low-resolution. Since DWT is invertible, there is no loss of information despite the downsampling scheme. Moreover, DWT can capture spatio-temporal information of feature maps [107], which helps to preserve detailed texture. Table 3 sums up the key features of the aforementioned methods.

VI. SUPERVISED ADVERSARIAL DEFENSE MECHANISMS

In the section will be presented input transformation defenses handcrafted specifically for adversarial noise only. Their

TABLE 3. Learning methods for image restoration to non-adversarial noise.

Authors/ Year	Methods	Applications	Functionality	Pros/Cons
Jain et al [91] 2008	CNN	Blind gaussian denoising	Simple CNN for natural image denoising	It can be applied to novel forms of imagery. However, training CNNs is computationally expensive and very difficult to understand their structure.
Xie et al [92] 2012	CNN	Blind gaussian denoising	Combines sparse coding and deep networks pre-trained with denoising auto-encoder (DA)	It can be adapted to other tasks and is a suitable choice for fully automatic and noise pattern specific image processing. However, it can remove only specific noise patterns.
Burger et al (2012) [94]	CNN	Gaussian image denoising	Patch-based denoising algorithm that is learned on a large dataset with a plain neural network	It competes with state-of-the-art image denoising methods, but it cannot generalize well to other noise levels.
Schmidt et al (2014) [98]	NN	Image restoration	Introduced cascade of shrinkage field	It is a novel random field model applicable to the restoration of high-resolution images with fast runtime and high restoration quality.
Mao et al (2016) [106]	CNN	Image restoration	Multiple layers of convolution and deconvolution operators aiming to learn end-to-end mappings	It achieves better performance than state-of-the-art methods on image denoising and super-resolution.
Chen et al (2017) [99]	NN	Image restoration/ JPEG deblocking	Nonlinear reaction-diffusion models for various image restoration problems	It has a simple structure and is faster than all competing algorithms. It is also applicable to the restoration of high-resolution images. However, ground truth needs to be defined and it cannot handle all the noise levels.
Zhang et al (2017) [90]	CNN	Gaussian image denoising / super-resolution / JPEG deblocking	CNN with residual learning and batch normalization	It can three denoising tasks, including Gaussian denoising with unknown noise level, single image super-resolution with multiple upscaling factors, and JPEG image deblocking with different quality factors.
Tai et al (2017) [112]	CNN	Image restoration	A DL persistent network is proposed that includes a memory block	It handles image denoising, super-resolution and JPEG deblocking, achieving better performance over the state of the art.
Zhang et al (2017) [107]	CNN	Image denoising	A model-based optimization method based on a set of fast and effective CNN denoisers	It results in a flexible, fast and effective framework for various image restoration tasks. It can handle various tasks and can be utilized as a good alternative to model image prior.
Zhang et al (2018) [108]	CNN	Blind denoising	CNN with a tunable noise level map as the input for blind denoising	It can control the trade-off between noise reduction and detail preservation. It is able to handle additive white Gaussian and real noise. It is faster than other competing methods.
Liu et al (2018) [110]	CNN	Gaussian image denoising, super-resolution and JPEG deblocking	Modified U-Net architecture with wavelet for image restoration	It can enlarge receptive field with a better tradeoff between efficiency and performance. It can handle multiple restoration tasks, such as image denoising, single image super-resolution and JPEG compression artifact removal.
He et al (2019) [109]	CNN	Image restoration	Model can be adapted to multiple restoration levels, by performing channel-wise feature modification	In can be adapted to any restoration level by directly adjusting the AdaFM layers without an additional training stage.

main goal is to remove adversarial perturbations from data before feeding them to the target model. Multiple categories of methods trained on adversarial can be used as a defense mechanism for adversarial examples, especially on AVs. These refer to input rectification, auto-encoders and generative adversarial networks (GANs).

A. INPUT RECTIFICATION

A huge variety of papers [58], [59], [109], [110] has been published aiming to alleviate adversarial examples using preprocessing techniques. The main reason why these preprocessing methods achieve satisfactory results is that many preprocessing operations are non-differentiable, thus restricting the feasibility of gradient-based adversarial perturbations. Prakash *et al.* [111] built an algorithm to process the input image and remove any adversarial manipulation before feeding it to the target model. More specifically, the proposed technique forced the image to match natural image characteristics, via a method called pixel deflection. This method corrupted the input image by redistributing pixel values and

then a wavelet-based denoising operation was responsible for softening both this corruption and any adversarial perturbation. Multiple experiments were conducted in the dataset of Imagenet [98], achieving satisfactory results against a variety of robust attacks. Das *et al.* [74] generated the Shield defense framework, which is a compression-based approach to combat adversarial attacks. The proposed technique combined randomization, vaccination and ensembling into a final robust model to adversaries. Das *et al.* explored JPEG's flexibility in supporting multiple compression levels to build ensemble robust models. To immunize the model from artifacts introduced by compression, a vaccination technique was proposed by training on compressed images. Moreover, another layer was added, to provide randomization during the compression process. As a result, the adversary could not estimate the actual transformation that was performed to the input image. Finally, multiple experiments were conducted using the ImageNet dataset [98]. This mechanism was compared with unsupervised techniques, such as median filter and total variation denoising techniques and achieved better

results when facing high perturbation delivered by I-FGSM and FGSM attacks.

B. AUTO-ENCODER

An auto-encoder refers to a neural network trained to copy its input to its output. The goal of these types of models is to discover useful properties of the data, leveraging simpler hidden representations of them. Meng and Chen [112] proposed Magnet, a new framework for mitigating adversarial perturbations. It is comprised of one or more separate detector networks and a reformer network. The first one refers to a function, which is responsible for detecting adversarial attacks. Hence, the detector rejects the input which does not approximate the manifold of normal examples. The reformer network aims to reconstruct the input data, by moving them towards the manifold of normal examples. Then the reconstructed data are fed to the target classifier. Overall, the proposed method was evaluated on the datasets of MNIST [60] and CIFAR-10 [61]. The experiments showed that the proposed method is effective against the most advanced state-of-the-art attacks in both black-box and grey-box attacks. However, Samangouei *et al.* showed that Defense-GAN [113] performed better from the defense mechanism of MagNet in their experiments. Furthermore, Song *et al.* [67] proposed a defense mechanism to adversaries named PixelDefend, which is a model-agnostic and attack-agnostic method. Song *et al.* proved that adversarial examples mainly belong to the low probability regions of the training distribution. To estimate the training distribution of input data, the PixelCNN model [114] was utilized. Hence, the core idea of the proposed method is to purify input data, by transforming them back towards the training distribution, solving an optimization function. As a result, only the purified image, which is closer to the training distribution will be given to the target model. Finally, PixelDefend was evaluated in the datasets of Fashion MNIST [115] and CIFAR-10 [68] and proved to be very effective in a wide variety of attacks. Moosavi-Dezfooli *et al.* [116] submitted a new non-differentiable algorithm as a defense mechanism, known as D3. The input image is divided into multiple overlapping patches. Latter are being denoised independently with sparse reconstruction using a dictionary of patches. The patch selection algorithm manages to eliminate the effect of the adversaries and at the same time to maintain the accuracy of original inputs. The proposed method was evaluated under multiple settings in the datasets of CIFAR-10 [68] and ImageNet [98] and performs comparably results with the state-of-the-art defense techniques. Sun *et al.* [117] proposed an adversarial defense by Stratified Convolutional Sparse Coding (CSC) with many similarities with D3. It refers to an attack and model-agnostic defense mechanism, capable of removing adversarial perturbations at any scale. To achieve that a low-dimensional image space has been generated, using a convolution dictionary learning-based technique [118], [119], [120], [121]. Thus, the projected adversarial images into this new feature space will be closer

FIGURE 9. Proposed defense mechanism from [117] in steps: Feed input image to a Denoising Auto-Encoder (DAE), detect the cluster the input image belongs to, optimize filters and features maps referring to the selected cluster, image projection to feature space.

FIGURE 10. The pipeline of Defense-GAN [113].

to their original inputs, removing adversarial perturbations. The projection is implemented by a Space Transformation Layer (STL) between the input and first layer of the target model, using a set of filters and features maps for each filter. The overall proposed method, which is illustrated in Figure 9, outperformed state-of-the-art defense techniques in the datasets of CIFAR-10 [68] and ImageNet [98]. Finally, in contrast with D3 which reconstructs images in low-resolution datasets utilizing a very large natural patch dictionary, the proposed method is robust to input resolution, perturbation scale, and dataset scale using a small number of filters.

C. GAN

Goodfellow *et al.* [122] proposed a new framework of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) in 2014, suggesting that this area of research could prove useful. Alternative formulations have also been proposed in the literature. One of them refers to Wasserstein GANs (WGANs) by Arjovsky *et al.* [123] that utilizes the Wasserstein distance resulting in a different loss function. Based on WGANs, Samangouei *et al.* [113] proposed the Defense-GAN, which is shown in Figure 10. It is a new defense strategy taking into consideration GANs in order to improve the robustness of classification models against black-box and white-box adversarial perturbations. Multiple experiments were conducted using the datasets of MNIST [60] and Fashion-MNIST [115]. The proposed method was compared to adversarial training [13] and Magnet [112] under multiple white-box attacks and black-box attacks. The final results showed that Defense-GAN provide satisfactory results and outperformed MagNet [112], whereas other tested methods performed poorly on at least one type of attack. Table 4 sums up the key features of the aforementioned methods.

TABLE 4. Learning methods for image restoration to adversarial noise.

Authors/ Year	Methods	Applications	Functionality	Pros/Cons
Guo et al [59]/ 2018	Bit-depth reduction, JPEG compression, TV minimization, image quilting	Image denoising	Implement transformation techniques to input data before feeding them to a CNN model	Total variation minimization, image quilting, and related methods are stronger defenses than deterministic denoising procedures such as bit-depth reduction or JPEG compression. That is due to their non-differentiable nature and their inherent randomness.
Das et al [60]/ 2018	Deep Learning with JPEG compression	Image denoising & Model Vaccination	Create an ensemble of models by training on images of multiple levels of compression	Re-training a model with JPEG compressed images can remove adversarial perturbations. However, the accuracy of the model may be decreased if we have images of a small size.
Dziugaite et al [113]/ 2016	JPEG compression	Image denoising	JPG compression can alleviate manipulations from adversaries	JPG compression can reverse only small adversarial perturbations created by the Fast-Gradient-Sign method.
Xie et al [76] / 2018	Random resizing & padding	Image denoising	Apply randomization techniques to mitigate adversarial perturbations	The proposed randomization defense mechanism does not need additional training. It has very few additional computations and is compatible with other adversarial defense methods.
Luo et al [114]/ 2016	CNN	Image denoising	Generate foveation-based countermeasures to remove adversarial perturbations	The transformation of the image produced by a foveation decreases the effect of the adversary on the classification scores.
Prakash et al [115]/ 2018	Pixel Deflection	Image denoising	Image corruption utilizing a pixel deflection method and wavelet-based denoiser to alleviate adversarial examples	It is a computationally-efficient image transform that protects regions of interest, leading to effective defense mechanisms.
Das et al [75]/ 2018	Shield	Image denoising & Model Vaccination	Compression-based approach aiming to combat adversaries through randomization and vaccination	It is fast and successful without requiring knowledge about the model defense mechanism. However it cannot defend against all possible attacks, but it can be integrated as a preprocessing step into many approaches.
Meng et al [116]/ 2017	MagNet	Image denoising	Adversarial mitigation via one or more separate detector networks and a reformer network	It does not require either adversarial examples or the knowledge of the process for generating them, which leads to better generalization. However, the accuracy of the model may be decreased with stronger attacks.
Samangouei et al [117]/ 2018	Defense-GAN	Image reconstruction	Defense mechanism using Wasserstein GANs	This method is effective against the most commonly considered attack methods. However, training GANs is still a challenging task and an active area of research.
Song et al [68]/ 2018	PixelDefend	Image reconstruction	Refine input data, by transforming them back towards the training distribution	It is model agnostic and attack-agnostic, which means it can be integrated with other approaches to provide better defense mechanisms.
Dezfooli et al [120]/ 2019	D3	Image reconstruction	A patch-based denoiser aiming to create strong classifiers via sparse reconstruction and dictionary-based methods	It is a novel patch-based denoising algorithm against adversarial attacks. However, there is a tradeoff between clean image accuracy and robustness against the attacks.
Sun et al [121]/ 2019	Stratified Convolutional Sparse Coding	Image reconstruction	A low-dimensional quasi-natural image space was created aiming to remove manipulations from adversaries	It is an attack agnostic adversarial defense approach with additionally increased robustness to input resolution, perturbation scale, and dataset scale. However, there is a trade-off between the projection image quality and defense robustness.

VII. DATASET

The Carla [39] simulator was used to generate multiple data for the training, validation, and testing phase of the algorithms. Carla was developed to be an Application Programming Interface capable of handling various and complex tasks related to autonomous driving. Multiple scenarios could be generated using this simulator that would be very difficult to implement in the real world, such as collisions between cars and pedestrians. Hence, it could assist researchers and enterprises to validate their algorithms before testing them in real-world cases. Most of the publicly available datasets for autonomous vehicles [41], [124] are mainly captured during daytime with good/medium weather

conditions which do not always represent reality. However, the Carla simulator has integrated multiple environments, such as rural, highway, city, etc and multiple weather conditions could be applied to each one of them. That makes it more practical for real-time applications since more use-cases could be extracted for the training of deep learning models.

A benchmark dataset was generated to conduct our experiments in this paper. The generated dataset contains 23 different classes which are illustrated in Table 6. It consists of multiple images with a size of 1280×960 pixels, captured from car-mounted cameras with dynamic weather conditions. More specifically, a basic town layout with multiple

TABLE 5. Existing libraries on adversarial attacks and defenses that can be applied to AVs.

Authors / Year	Domain
DeepRobust [129]	Adversarial library for attack and defense methods on images and graphs implemented. Supports: Pytorch.
Adversarial-library [130]	Adversarial attacks implemented in PyTorch. The code was implemented to maximize efficiency.
Adversarial Robustness Toolbox (ART) [131]	ART is a Python library that provides tools to defend and evaluate ML models and applications against adversarial threats. ART supports all popular machine learning frameworks and all data types and machine learning tasks (classification, object detection, speech recognition, generation, certification, etc.).
Foolbox [132]	Python library that lets you easily run adversarial attacks against ML models like deep neural networks. It is built on top of EagerPy. Supports: JAX, PyTorch, and TF2.
CleverHans [133]	Python library to benchmark machine learning systems vulnerability to adversarial examples. Supports: JAX, PyTorch, and TF2.

FIGURE 11. The distribution of 2D semantic labels over 10k generated frames.

weather conditions, a complex city environment and a rural environment with narrow roads were used for the data generation. As regards the attached sensors to the ego-vehicle, an RGB and a semantic segmentation camera were utilized. The frames were selected to contain a large number of dynamic objects, varying scene layouts and backgrounds. The distribution of 2D semantic labels over 10k generated frames is shown in Pie 11. For visualization purposes only, the labels Unlabeled, Other, Bridge, RailTrack, GuardRail, Dynamic, Fence, Terrain and Water are merged in the class Others. Also, version 0.9.12 of the Carla simulator was utilized. Finally, some generated data are illustrated in Table 7. The whole dataset could be found in the following link: CarlaScenes.

Finally, for performing adversarial attacks with the provided dataset there are several open-source libraries. Libraries in [125], [126], [127], [128], [129] provide the basic tools to perform attacks, apply defenses and evaluate ML models or applications against adversarial threats. The most well-maintained repositories and libraries are presented in Table 5 and a dedicated review is provided in [130].

TABLE 6. Tags from semantic segmentation images extracted from CARLA [39].

Id	Tag	Description
0	Unlabeled	Elements that have not been categorized are considered Unlabeled.
1	Building	Buildings like houses, skyscrapers,... and the elements attached to them.
2	Fence	Barriers, railing, or other upright structures.
3	Other	Everything that does not belong to any other category.
4	Pedestrian	Humans that walk or ride/drive any kind of vehicle or mobility system.
5	Pole	Small mainly vertically oriented pole.
6	RoadLine	The markings on the road.
7	Road	Part of ground on which cars usually drive.
8	SideWalk	Part of ground designated for pedestrians or cyclists.
9	Vegetation	Trees, hedges, all kinds of vertical vegetation.
10	Vehicles	Cars, vans, trucks, motorcycles, bikes, buses, trains.
11	Wall	Individual standing walls.
12	TrafficSign	Signs installed by the state/city authority, usually for traffic regulation.
13	Sky	Open sky. Includes clouds and the sun.
14	Ground	Any horizontal ground-level structures that do not match any other category.
15	Bridge	Only the structure of the bridge.
16	RailTrack	All kinds of rail tracks that are non-drivable by cars.
17	GuardRail	All types of guard rails/crash barriers.
18	TrafficLight	Traffic lightboxes without their poles.
19	Static	Elements in the scene and props that are immovable.
20	Dynamic	Elements whose position is susceptible to change over time.
21	Water	Horizontal water surfaces.
22	Terrain	Grass, ground-level vegetation, soil or sand.

VIII. EXPERIMENTS

Based on the literature, there is a gap in the development of stable algorithms aiming to remove exclusively the adversarial noise from the data. However, there are plenty of classical denoising methods targeting other types of noise, such as gaussian or random, etc. Hence, the scope of this section is to examine whether classical restoration techniques could alleviate the adversarial noise as well. To accomplish that, we generated a benchmark dataset utilizing the Carla simulator. Hence, this section is oriented to a small evaluation of deep learning denoising techniques using our dataset. Regarding models trained on non-adversarial noise, three approaches [88], [104], [105] have been tested. Based on Table 3, they can be utilized in a variety of applications, such as gaussian image denoising, blind denoising and image restoration. DnCNN [88] model has been trained to handle Gaussian denoising with unknown noise level (i.e., random noise, blind Gaussian denoising). While for the rest of the models [104], [105] the level of noise was estimated, using techniques as in [131], [132]. Then the respective model with the adjusted weights was used to handle this specific perturbation. That helps the whole procedure identify the restoration level necessary since in case of an adversarial attack the perturbation magnitude is typically unknown. Regarding models trained on adversarial noise, there is a limited number of methods in the literature. In our

TABLE 7. Benchmark dataset using CARLA simulator: RGB images and segmentation outputs for multiple environments and weather conditions.

case, CSC [117] was utilized, referring to a model-agnostic defense mechanism to adversarial perturbations.

A. SETTINGS

Untargeted and targeted adversarial attacks were implemented to evaluate our results. As a result, FGSM, BIM and PGD were used for the untargeted case, as MomentumIterative and LinfPGD for the targeted case. The number of iterations of iterative attacks is set to 10 and the step-size is equal to 1, meaning that the value of each pixel could be changed by one every iteration. Adversarial perturbation ϵ causes a model to change its original prediction when added to the original input. Hence, ϵ is a hyper-parameter governing the distance between adversarial and original image. The smaller the magnitude of the perturbation, the less imperceptible will be the attack to the human eye. The previous attacks were evaluated setting the perturbation ϵ to each value from {1, 3, 5, 7}.

B. EVALUATION

The performance is measured in terms of pixel intersection-over-union (IoU). It is defined as the area of overlap between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth, divided by the area of union between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth. IoU is one of the most common metrics in semantic segmentation. To highlight the impact of a preceding denoising block, the behavior of Deeplabv3 [54] model was evaluated on attacked images that have been firstly denoised. Deeplabv3 is a state-of-art deep learning model for semantic image segmentation, aiming to assign a semantic label to every pixel in the input image. Several trained denoising models and configurations were examined in the evaluation process

TABLE 8. IoU % results of models trained on non-adversarial noise aiming to mitigate untargeted adversarial attacks for the levels of perturbations 1/3/5/7 for an image with size 1280 × 960.

Method	Clean	Attacked	Adam [109]	DnCNN [90]	FFDNet [108]
FGSM	74	71/60/42/31	60/60/59/55	61/59/55/52	64/64/61/55
BIM	74	32/04/01/00	72/23/03/02	55/30/09/04	60/24/00/00
PGD	74	73/64/45/27	61/62/60/59	60/60/57/53	65/66/62/58

under multiple levels of attacks. By observing how well each model can reconstruct the image, a robust segmentation model was generated. The experiments for the denoising part were conducted on pre-trained models and the GitHub repositories of the papers [88], [104], [105], [117] were utilized. Finally, Deeplabv3 was trained on a CarlaScenes dataset by splitting randomly to a percentage of 70%, 20%, and 10% for training, validation, and testing purposes respectively. With a batch size of 16 images and a learning rate fixed to a value of 0.0001 the model was trained for 580 epochs and the reported accuracy was 79%.

C. RESULTS

Models trained on non-adversarial noise were evaluated firstly to examine how they respond to adversarial perturbations. These models are Adam [105], DnCNN [88] and FFDNet [104]. The results of the experiments referring to untargeted and targeted attack are illustrated in Tables 8 and 9 respectively. Table 8 shows the behavior of the aforementioned models in FGSM [13], BIM [49] and PGD [51] untargeted attacks while Table 9 focus on MomentumIterative [47] and LinfPGD targeted attacks. The majority of applications related to AVs utilize input images

TABLE 9. IoU % results of models trained on non-adversarial noise aiming to mitigate targeted adversarial attacks for the levels of perturbations 1/3/5/7 for an image with size 1280×960 .

Method	Clean	Attacked	Adam [109]	DnCNN [90]	FFDNet [108]
Momentum Iterative	74	72/49/31/17	61/60/61/54	62/56/56/50	65/65/62/60
LinfPGD	74	72/62/46/32	60/62/61/63	61/60/59/57	67/65/65/64

FIGURE 12. Adversarial attack and FFDNet [104] denoiser: from left to right and from top to bottom: original rgb image, noisy rgb image, denoised rgb image, original segmented image, attacked segmented image, denoised segmented image.

with dimensions 1280×960 . Hence, we generated multiple images of the previous dimensions to evaluate our results for multiple perturbations levels. The success of the segmentation model is evaluated in terms of IoU. For instance, the segmentation model for some attacked images generated by the BIM method ($\epsilon = 1$) has a mean accuracy of 32%, but it is increased after the integration of the denoising network to 55% using the (DnCNN [88]) and to 72% using the Adam [105] solution. Hence, the previous denoisers managed to restore the images, by removing most of the adversarial noise. However, in cases where the attack affects only slightly the segmentation output, the denoising impact is not very important. For instance, the impact of the FFDNet [104] denoising model when an FGSM attack was performed for $\epsilon = 1$ was not important, by reducing the accuracy of Deeplab from 71% to 64%. But, for bigger ϵ the denoisers produce more robust results and increase a lot the accuracy of the segmentation network.

Overall, taking into consideration Tables 8 and 9, it is concluded that the denoisers built for classical image restoration tasks, manage to remove the adversarial noise as well. Some qualitative results of denoised models trained on non-adversarial noise are illustrated in Table 10. The latter indicates the capability of denoisers to alleviate the adversarial manipulations. The method of FFDNet shows slightly better results than the rest of the denoisers. Another example of FFDNet denoiser is illustrated in Figure 12, in which the adversarial image has been restored.

The majority of models trained on adversarial noise aiming to remove the perturbation of the adversaries can only work on a limited range of resolutions. That makes them impractical to applications related to scene analysis operations in AVs. We selected the method of CSC [117] to evaluate our experiments, reshaping the images generated by the Carla simulator to the size of 224×224 pixels. The results for untargeted and targeted attacks, which are

illustrated in Tables 11 and 12 accordingly, show the ineffectiveness of this method to remove the manipulations of the adversaries. For instance, for the PGD untargeted attack, CSC denoiser does not improve the scene understanding for a small level of perturbation. The mean accuracy of the segmentation model for attacked images ($\epsilon = 1$) is about 50%, while CSC reaches 43% accuracy. For $\epsilon = 7$ the denoiser manages to improve the scene understanding from 17% to 27%. However, for scene analysis operations in an automated driving system, CSC denoiser cannot provide robust decisions. The same conclusion holds for the targeted attacks as well. Some qualitative results of the proposed method are illustrated also in Table 13, in which the scene analysis has been restored to some extent.

Based on the previous experiments, it is concluded that there is an increasing gap in the need for robust response mechanisms to adversarial attacks. Firstly, the experiments showed that denoising models trained on adversarial noise are capable of restoring the attacked images to some extent. However, the previous models cannot run in real-time applications in AVs, since they can work only on a limited range of resolutions (224×224 pixels). On the other hand, restoration models trained on non-adversarial noise indicated valuable results to adversarial perturbations, even with input images with dimensions 1280×960 pixels. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate denoising methods for adversarial degradation alongside other noise perturbations. Overall, more research should be conducted from the community, to provide robust models for removing the adversarial attacks.

IX. FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Due to the high increase of attacks aiming to manipulate the vehicle's behavior, the implementation of defense mechanisms has drawn great attention from both academia and industry. In this survey, we conduct a comprehensive review of the defense mechanism that can be used to subdue the effect of adversarial noise along with a thorough analysis of their availability and limitation in the AV domain. We will now summarize the possible future research directions to improve the robustness of deep-learning modules used for perception.

A. CREATE MORE GENERIC DEFENSE MECHANISMS FOR ADVERSARIAL PERTURBATION

Based on the literature, there is a growing gap in the need for secure and stable algorithms running in AVs. Even though since Szegedy *et al.* [4] there are numerous published papers with adversarial attacks, almost every defense mechanism has an effect for limited attack types. Hence, the majority of them fail to alleviate the adversarial manipulations to unseen attacks. Another constraint of the existing models trained for adversarial noise removal is that they can work only on a small range of resolutions, making them impractical for safety-critical applications. Adding to that the computational overhead that adds to the perception task is not attainable for the resource-constrained AVs. Therefore, the development of novel, less computation expensive defense strategies

TABLE 10. Qualitative results of models trained on non-adversarial noise for images with size 1280 × 960.

TABLE 11. IoU % results of model trained on adversarial noise aiming to mitigate untargeted adversarial attacks for the levels of perturbations 1/3/5/7 for an image with size 224 × 224.

Method	Clean	Attacked	CSC[121]
FGSM	53	48/36/25/18	42/35/29/23
BIM	53	17/05/02/00	23/08/05/03
PGD	53	50/40/27/17	43/37/33/27

TABLE 12. IoU % results of model trained on adversarial noise aiming to mitigate targeted adversarial attacks for the levels of perturbations 1/3/5/7 for an image with size 224 × 224.

Method	Clean	Attacked	CSC[121]
Momentum Iterative	53	49/34/19/11	43/37/30/23
LinfPGD	53	51/40/29/20	44/40/36/31

(e.g., using acceleration techniques [133], [134], [135]) that can handle a more generic model of adversarial perturbation should be further studied.

B. INVESTIGATE THE DENOISING CAPABILITY OF EXISTING METHODS TO HANDLE ADVERSARIES

It would be beneficial for the community of adversarial robustness to be adopted in the more general scheme of image degradations. Firstly, measuring corruption robustness is significantly easier than measuring adversarial robustness. According to [136] to compute adversarial robustness requires solving an NP-hard problem. Secondly, exposing the adversarial noise-robust model to other types of noise may reveal, unknown until now, failure modes. Autonomous driving requires models that are perfectly robust in the appearance of corruptions of any kind, to ensure both stability and integrity. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate methods robust for adversarial degradation alongside other noise corruptions. The evaluation should be performed on a common evaluation base.

TABLE 13. Qualitative results of model trained on adversarial noise for images with size 224 × 224.

C. ENHANCE EXISTING LIBRARIES

Most common open-source tools (Table 5) that perform adversarial attacks, defenses, or evaluation focus on classification or speech recognition models. So investigating how to adapt those tools to handle segmentation or regression models remains future work. Furthermore, none of the tools boxes is dedicated to deep learning-based automotive applications.

D. LIDAR ADVERSARIAL ATTACKS

Vision perception systems may be used by the majority of the automotive industry but in the upcoming years, they will be enhanced using information from raw point clouds. Though most of the existing papers examining adversarial perturbations focus on image data. Investigating the effect of adversarial attacks in perception modules utilizing raw point clouds is still an open field for further improvement.

X. CONCLUSION

In this paper a thorough investigation of various scene analysis strategies, robust to adversarial attacks, is provided. A detailed taxonomy of defense mechanisms for countering manipulations from adversaries is then presented, identifying the following categories: i) those that modify the data, ii) those that propose adding extra models, and iii) those that focus on modifying the models deployed for scene analysis. Also, a more detailed analysis is carried out related to the methods that are utilizing input transformation operations as countermeasures. An extensive evaluation study was carried out utilizing the deep learning-based supervised approaches that have been either proposed for image restoration or adversarial noise removal. Finally, some challenges and future actions are presented to allow other researchers to create robust solutions and eliminate the existing security gaps that have not been addressed at a satisfactory level. The dataset that was created for the sake of this study using the CARLA autonomous driving simulator is also public and can be utilized for the development and benchmarking of DL-based solutions focused on automotive applications.

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